

BEHAVIOUR OF NITROPHENOLS WITH *p*-TOLUENE SULPHONYL
CHLORIDE. PART V. ABNORMAL BEHAVIOUR OF SOME
DINITROPHENOLS WITH METHYL GROUP IN
THE *META* POSITION

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Behaviour of 4-bromo-3-methyl-2:6-dinitrophenol, 3:5-dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenol and 4-chloro-3:5-dimethyl-2:6-dinitrophenol has been studied. They are all found to form *p*-toluene sulphonic acid esters in sodium carbonate solution.

Abnormal behaviour of some dinitrophenols has been observed by several workers (Ullmann and co-workers, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1870; 1911, 44, 3731; Sane and Joshi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 2481; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 299; 1932, 9, 59; Sen, *ibid.*, 1946, 28, 53). One of such an abnormality manifests itself in the replacement of the hydroxyl group by a chlorine atom when heated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and diethylaniline in the case of those nitrophenols in which the nitro groups are either in the *ortho* positions or in the *ortho* and *para* positions to the hydroxyl group. By heating these nitrophenols with the acid chloride and an aqueous solution of sodium carbonate, *p*-toluene sulphonic esters are obtained. If these nitrophenols have a chlorine atom in the *meta* position, it shows hardly any effect in their behaviour, but a methyl group in the *meta* position exerts in some cases a marked influence. In a few cases the hydroxyl group is replaced by chlorine, whilst in others it is not so. They are, however, readily converted into their sulphonic acid esters.

The behaviour of these esters towards ammonia, aniline, etc. is not similar. The esters of all those dinitrophenols in which the hydroxyl is replaced by chlorine are found to be reactive, $-O.SO_2.C_6H_4$ group being replaced by $-NH_2$, $-NHPh$, etc. group. The esters of those nitrophenols that have a methyl group in the *meta* position do not behave in one way. Some esters such as those of 4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol and 2-iodo-4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol are reactive, whereas others such as those of 4-chloro-2:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol and 3:6-dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenol are unreactive under similar conditions.

In the present communication the behaviour of 4-bromo-3-methyl-2:6-dinitrophenol, 3:5-dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenol and 4-chloro-3:5-dimethyl-2:6-dinitrophenol has been studied. They all form *p*-toluene sulphonic esters in sodium carbonate solution. The first one forms only the sulphonic acid ester when heated with the acid chloride and diethylaniline, whilst the last two do not form even an ester under similar conditions. In none of these cases the hydroxyl is replaced by chlorine. All these esters are quite stable and unreactive towards ammonia and aniline.

EXPERIMENTAL

3:5-Dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenol.—To a mixture of sulphuric acid (34 c.c., *d* 1.58) and nitric acid (24 c.c., *d* 1.33) was added 3:5-dimethylphenol (10 g.) in small quanti-

ties with vigorous stirring. The product was then heated on a water-bath with occasional shaking till all the nitrous fumes were removed. It was then cooled, filtered, washed with hot water and crystallised from 75% acetic acid, when light yellow crystals were obtained, m.p. 106° ; it is insoluble in water, slightly soluble in alcohol and easily soluble in acetic acid. The white crystals of its acetate melt at 148° and of benzoate, prepared with benzoyl chloride in presence of either pyridine or sodium acetate, melt at 156° .

Under similar conditions 4-chloro-3:5-dimethylphenol yielded on nitration yellow crystals of 4-chloro-3:5-dimethyl-2:6-dinitrophenol, turning scarlet-red on heating and melting with swelling at 180° and dissolving in solvents as in the above compound. The white crystals of its acetate melt at 108° and of benzoate, at 125° .

4-Bromo-3-methyl-2:6-dinitrophenyl-p-toluene Sulphonate.—*p*-Toluenesulphonyl chloride (2.4 g.) and sodium carbonate (3 g.) were added to a boiling mixture of 4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol (3 g.) and water (10 c.c.) in small quantities with vigorous shaking. When the smell of the acid chloride had disappeared, a solid was separated by filtration. It was washed with hot sodium carbonate solution and crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and acetone, m.p. 158° . It is slightly soluble in alcohol and more so in acetone. (Found: S, 7.02. $C_{11}H_{11}O_7N_2BrS$ requires S, 7.42 per cent). The same ester was obtained by heating the substituted cresol with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and diethylaniline on a water-bath for 4 hours.

Under similar conditions 3:5-dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenol yielded 3:5 dimethyl-2:6-dinitrophenyl-*p*-toluene sulphonate, m.p. 171° (Found: S, 9.12. $C_{18}H_{14}O_7N_2S$ requires S, 8.74 per cent) and 4-chloro-3:5-dimethyl-2:6-dinitrophenyl-*p*-toluene sulphonate, m.p. 199° (Found: S, 7.71. $C_{18}H_{13}O_7N_2SCl$ requires S, 8.0 per cent) having similar solubilities. From these two substituted xylenols, neither an ester nor a chloro compound was obtained when they were heated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and diethylaniline.